

INGLIZCHA METALLURGIK TERMINLARNING O'ZBEK TILIDA TARJIMASI BO'YICHA MULOHAZALAR

Q.D.To'xtayeva, G.F.Erkinova

Navoiy davlat universiteti talabasi

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada metallurgik terminlarning o'zbek tilida tarjimasini aniqlash bo'yicha olib borilgan izlanishlar yuzasidan ma'lumotlar keltirilgan bo'lib, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda rivojlanib borayotgan kon-metallurgiya sohasiga yetuk mahalliy mutaxassislarni tayyorlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: metal, metallurgiya, gidrometallurgiya, pirometallurgiya, rangli metallar, nodir metallar, noyob metallar, qora metallar.

Fan va texnika taraqqiyoti, turli sohalarning ravnaq topib borayotgani terminologiyaga ham katta vazifalar yuklamoqda. Unda o'rganilishi va tadqiq etilishi kerak bo'lgan ko'plab soha terminlarini tasniflash va turlarga ajratish vazifasi dolzarbligicha qolmoqda. Terminlar ilmiy kashfiyotlar, tadqiqotlar hamda nazariy va amaliy natijalarda o'z ifodasini topadi. Terminlar maxsus kasbiy sohalardagi kommunikatsiya, u yoki bu kasbiy sohada yuzaga kelayotgan hodisalar, konsepsiyalar, fenomenlarni tavsiflash vositasi sanaladi. Bu tabiiy ravishda ingliz va o'zbek tilida terminlarni tartibga solish, unifikatsiya qilish va tizimlashtirish zaruratini tug'diradi.

Quyida misol tariqasida «Metals-Metallar», «Metallurgy-Metallurgiya», «Pyrometallurgical process - pirometallurgik jarayon», «Hydrometallurgy - gidrometallurgiya» va «Leaching-tanlab eritish» kabi terminlarning o'zbek tilida tarjimasini va izohini keltirib o'tamiz.

Metals – simple substances possessing high heat and electrical conductivity, luster, malleability and other properties. These properties are due to presence of large number of mobile electrons in crystalline lattice. About 80 elements belong to metals. They are divided into ferrous and non-ferrous metals. Ferrous metals include iron and its alloys. The rest are non-ferrous metals. Non-ferrous metals by properties and abundance in nature are classified as follows: Light metals: Al, Ti, Mg, Be, Li, Na, K, Ca, Rb, Sr, Ba; Heavy non-ferrous metals: Cu, Ni, Co, Pb, Sn, Zn, Cd, Sb, Bi, Hg; Refractory non-ferrous metals: W, Mo, Nb, Ta, V, Re, Cr, Zr, Hf; Precious metals: Au, Ag, Pt and platinoids; scattered metals: Tl, In, Nb; radioactive metals: Th, Pa, U, Np, Pu, Am, Cm, Bk, Cf, Es, Fm, Md, No, Lr. Metals used in limited production volume are called rare metals.

Metallar – yuqori issiqlik va elektr o'tkazuvchanlikka, yaltiroqlikka, bolg'alanuvchanlikka va boshqa xossalarga ega bo'lgan oddiy modda. Uning bu xususiyatlari durlik panjarasida juda ko'p harakatchan elektronlar borligigandandir. Metallarga 80 ga yaqin elementlar kiradi. Ular qora va rangli metallarga bo'linadi. Qora metallarga temir va uning qotishmalari kiradi. Qolganlari esa rangli metallardir. Rangli metallar xossalari va tabiatda tarqalishga qarab quyidagicha tasniflanadi: Yengil metallar: Al, Ti, Mg, Be, Li, Na, K, Ca, Rb, Sr, Ba; Og'ir rangli metallar: Cu, Ni, Co, Pb, Sn, Zn, Cd, Sb, Bi, Hg; Qiyin eruvchan rangli metallar: W, Mo, Nb, Ta, V, Re, Cr, Zr, Hf; Nodir metallar: Au, Ag, Pt va platinoidlar; tarqoq

metallar: Tl, In, Nb; radiofaol metallar: Th, Pa, U, Np, Pu, Am, Cm, Bk, Cf, Es, Fm, Md, No, Lr kiradi. Chegaralangan hajmda ishlab chiqarishda ishlatiladigan metallar noyob metallar deb ataladi.

Metallurgy – science, technology and industry branch including processes of extracting metals from ores and other materials, obtaining alloys and studying their properties. In addition, includes primary processing of ore extracted from bowels – crushing, grinding, beneficiation, drying, roasting, etc. Processes of obtaining metals, their refining, obtaining alloys and giving them necessary shape, structure and properties. Metallurgy is divided into two parts: ferrous metallurgy and non-ferrous metals metallurgy. Ferrous metallurgy includes production of iron and its alloys (pig iron, steel and ferroalloys), manganese, chromium, vanadium. Non-ferrous metals metallurgy includes production of remaining metals in D.I. Mendeleev's table, including radioactive elements. In turn, methods of pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, electrometallurgy, powder metallurgy, etc. are used to extract metals from ores.

Metallurgiya – fan, texnika va sanoat sohasi bo‘lib, ruda va boshqa materiallardan metallarni ajratib olish, qotishmalar olish va ularning xossalarini o‘rganish jarayonlari kiradi. Bundan tashqari, yer qa‘ridan qazib olingan rudaga birlamchi ishlov berish – maydalash, tuyish, boyitish, quritish, kuydirish va hokazo. Metallarni olish, tozalash, qotishmalar olib ularga kerakli shakl, struktura va xossalar berish jarayonlari kiradi. Metallurgiya ikkiga bo‘linadi: qora metallurgiya va rangli metallar metallurgiyasi. Qora metallar metallurgiyasiga temir va uning qotishmalari (cho‘yan, po‘lat va ferroqotishmalar), marganets, xrom, vanadiylarni ishlab chiqarish kiradi. Rangli metallar metallurgiyasiga D.I. Mendeleev jadvalidagi qolgan metallar, jumladan radiofaol elementlarni ishlab chiqarish kiradi. O‘z navbatida metallarni rudalardan ajratib olish uchun pirometallurgiya, gidrometallurgiya, elektrometallurgiya, kukun metallurgiya va hokazo usullaridan foydalaniladi.

Pyrometallurgical process – metallurgical process carried out at high temperature, processed material may partially or completely melt: roasting, smelting, converting, purification, distillation, etc. Pyrometallurgical process is main method in production of pig iron, steel, Pb, Cu, Ni and other metals.

Pirometallurgik jarayon – yuqori haroratda olib boriladigan, ishlov berilayotgan material qisman yoki to‘liq suyuqlanishi mumkin bo‘lgan metallurgik jarayon: kuydirish, eritish, konvertrlash, tozalash, distillyatsiyalash va hokazo. Cho‘yan, po‘lat, Pb, Cu, Ni va boshqa metallarni ishlab chiqarishda pirometallurgik jarayon asosiy usul hisoblanadi.

Hydrometallurgy – dissolution of metals from ores, concentrates and various metallurgical wastes using aqueous solutions of chemical reagents with transfer to solution and subsequent extraction from solution. Hydrometallurgy includes processes of ore treatment (grinding, classification, thickening), changing chemical composition of ore or concentrate (roasting, decomposition), selective dissolution, dewatering, washing, filtration, settling, purification from undesirable impurities, precipitation of metals and their compounds from solutions, treatment of precipitates.

Gidrometallurgiya – metallarni rudalar, boyitmalar va turli metallurgiya chiqindilaridan kimyoviy reagentlarning suvli eritmaları yordamida eritib, eritmaga o‘tkazish va keyin ularni eritmadan ajratib olish. Gidrometallurgiya rudaga ishlov berish (maydalash, tasniflash, quyultirish), ruda yoki boyitmaning kimyoviy tarkibini o‘zgartirish (qizdirish, parchalash), tanlab eritish, suvsizlantirish, yuvish, suzish, tindirish, keraksiz aralashmalardan tozalash,

metallar va ularning birikmalarini eritmalardan cho‘ktirish, cho‘kmalarga ishlov berish kabi jarayonlardan iborat.

Leaching – extraction individual components of a solid material using a solvent, based on the ability of the extracted substance to dissolve better than other components during hydrometallurgical extraction of metals from ores. Solutions of ammonia, acids, alkalis, metal or chlorine chlorides, sulfates, etc. can be used as a solvent. Leaching may be accompanied by oxidation of the extracted material in order to convert sparingly soluble compounds into readily soluble ones (oxidative leaching). Gases (usually air, oxygen), liquid and solid inorganic substances (HNO_3 , MnO_2 , KMnO_4 , etc.), bacteria (bacterial leaching) are used as oxidizers. Leaching is carried out at atmospheric and elevated (autoclave leaching) pressures.

Tanlab eritish - ruda va boyitmalardan erituvchilar ishtirokida boshqa komponentlarga qaraganda yaxshi eriydigan komponentlarni maxsus sharoitlarda eritmaga o‘tkazish jarayoni. Erituvchilar sifatida ammiak, kislotalar, ishqorlar va tuzlarning eritmaları ishlatilishi mumkin. Tanlab eritish ajratib olinayotgan metallni qiyin eruvchan birikma holdan oson eruvchan birikma holiga o‘tkazish maqsadida oksidlash yo‘li bilan ham borishi mumkin. Oksidlovchilar sifatida gazlar (havo, kislorod) suyuq va qattiq anorganik moddalar (HNO_3 , MnO_2 , KMnO_4 va b.) va bakteriyalar ishlatilishi mumkin. Tanlab eritish atmosfera bosimida yoki yuqori bosimda (avtoklavda) olib borilishi mumkin.

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